

The configuration quality theorem

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1 Preliminary definitions

1.1 TDOA

$TDOA_{ij}$ between 2 microphones mic_i and mic_j is the Time-Difference Of signal Arrival from sound source to these microphones .

Note. Knowing $TDOA_{ij}$ (pairwise TDOAs of N microphones mic_i , $1 \leq i \leq N$), we know the differences of distances \vec{R}_i from microphones \vec{mic}_i to sound source position \vec{x} : $c \cdot TDOA_{ij} = |\vec{R}_j - \vec{R}_i|$, where c is the sound speed. Therefore, knowing $TDOA_{ij}$, it is possible to calculate this sound source position \vec{x} using numerical optimization methods.

1.2 Configuration and Configuration quality

The configuration of N microphones mic_i ($1 \leq i \leq N$) is their positions in space (their coordinate vectors \vec{mic}_i).

The quality of configuration of microphones is the measure of how precise the sound source position \vec{x} can be estimated using the measured TDOAs and knowing its precision ($|\Delta TDOA|$ or, simply written, $\Delta TDOA$).

The quality of configuration of microphones can be expressed as the ratio between error of sound source location ($|\Delta x|$ or, simply written, Δx) and corresponding error of its measured TDOAs ($\Delta TDOA$). It can be expressed in a formula $\frac{c\Delta TDOA}{\Delta x}$, where c is the sound speed.

Note. If the configuration quality $\frac{\Delta TDOA}{\Delta x}$ is big, then small location errors Δx correspond to big TDOA errors ($\Delta TDOA$), which can be written as $\Delta TDOA = \frac{\Delta TDOA}{\Delta x} \cdot \Delta x$. Therefore, given estimation of TDOAs, finding \vec{x} by optimization algorithms is more robust to errors of this TDOA estimation.

2 Formulation of the theorem

If the sound source at position \vec{x} and distance \vec{R}_i from microphones \vec{mic}_i ($1 \leq i \leq N$) is located with precision Δx (is located inside the sphere with a radius Δx , centered at \vec{x}), then its mean TDOA error is

$$\Delta TDOA(\vec{x}) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{5} \frac{|\Delta x|}{c} \sqrt{\sum_{i < j}^N (1 - \cos \Delta_{ij}(\vec{x}))}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{20} \frac{|\Delta x|}{c} \sqrt{N! / (N-2)! - 2 \sum_{i < j}^N \cos \Delta_{ij}(\vec{x})}}$$

Or, in other words, the configuration quality is $\frac{\Delta TDOA(\vec{x})}{\Delta x} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{5}} \sqrt{\sum_{i < j}^N (1 - \cos \Delta_{ij}(\vec{x}))} / c$

Note. The mean error here is the root of the mean squared error (mean over all possible locations $\vec{x} + \vec{\Delta x}$ corresponding to precision Δx). The root of mean squared error corresponds to the euclidian distance in the error space.

3 Proof of the theorem

Let us take a pair of microphones \overrightarrow{mic}_i and \overrightarrow{mic}_j . If location-error $\vec{\Delta x}$, is known, then the squared $TDOA_{ij}$ -error (TDOA difference at correct \vec{x} and erroneous $\vec{x} + \vec{\Delta x}$ positions) takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta TDOA_{ij}^2 &= (|\vec{\Delta x} \cdot \vec{R}_j|/|\vec{R}_j| - |\vec{\Delta x} \cdot \vec{R}_i|/|\vec{R}_i|)^2 / c^2 = \\ &= (\vec{\Delta x})^2 \cdot (\cos \angle(\vec{\Delta x}, \vec{R}_j) - \cos \angle(\vec{\Delta x}, \vec{R}_i))^2 / c^2. \end{aligned}$$

Let us calculate the mean squared TDOA-error $\Delta TDOA_{ij}^2$ for all position-errors $\vec{\Delta x}$ inside a sphere with a radius $\Delta x = |\vec{\Delta x}|$ centered around \vec{x} (all position-errors $\vec{\Delta x}$ corresponding to the precision Δx).

Let us parametrize this sphere (all directions $\vec{\Delta x}$) by angles α (rotation inside the (\vec{R}_i, \vec{R}_j) -plane, $\alpha = 0$ for $\vec{\Delta x}$ colinear to \vec{R}_i) and β (rotation perpendicular to this plane: $\beta = \pi/2$ for $\vec{\Delta x}$ inside the plane, $\beta = 0$ and $\beta = \pi$ for $\vec{\Delta x}$ perpendicular to it).

Then, using notation $\alpha = \angle(\vec{R}_i, \vec{\Delta x})$, $\Delta \alpha = \angle(\vec{R}_i, \vec{R}_j)$, the mean squared TDOA-error takes the following form.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta TDOA_{ij}^2 &= \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\text{SphereVolume}} \iiint r^2 (\cos(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) - \cos \alpha)^2 dV = \\ &= \frac{1}{\frac{4}{3}\pi \Delta x^3 c^2} \int_{r=0}^{\Delta x} r^2 \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} (\cos(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) - \cos \alpha)^2 r^2 \sin \beta d\alpha d\beta dr = \\ &= \frac{3}{4\pi \Delta x^3 c^2} \int_{r=0}^{\Delta x} r^4 dr \int_0^\pi \sin \beta d\beta \int_0^{2\pi} (\cos(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) - \cos \alpha)^2 d\alpha = \\ &= \frac{3}{4\pi \Delta x^3 c^2} \frac{r^5}{5} \Big|_0^{\Delta x} \cdot \int_0^\pi \sin \beta d\beta \cdot (\int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) d\alpha + \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2 \alpha d\alpha - \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \cos(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) \cos \alpha d\alpha) = \\ &= \frac{3}{4\pi \Delta x^3 c^2} \Delta x^5 / 5 \cdot I_1 (I_2 + I_3 - I_4). \end{aligned}$$

Let us calculate all terms I_i

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^\pi \sin \beta d\beta = -\cos \beta \Big|_0^\pi = 2 \\ I_2 &= \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2 \alpha d\alpha = \frac{1}{2} (\cos \alpha \sin \alpha) \Big|_0^{2\pi} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha \Big|_0^{2\pi} = \pi \\ I_3 &= \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) d\alpha = I_2 = \pi \\ I_4 &= \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \cos(\Delta \alpha - \alpha) \cos \alpha d\alpha = \\ &= \int_0^{2\pi} 2 (\cos \Delta \alpha \cos \alpha + \sin \Delta \alpha \sin \alpha) \cos \alpha d\alpha = \\ &= 2 \cos \Delta \alpha \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2 \alpha d\alpha + \sin \Delta \alpha \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha d\alpha = \\ &= 2 \cos \Delta \alpha \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2 \alpha d\alpha + \frac{1}{2} \sin \Delta \alpha \int_{2\alpha=0}^{2\alpha=4\pi} \sin 2\alpha d2\alpha = \\ &= 2 \cos \Delta \alpha \pi - \frac{1}{2} \sin \Delta \alpha \cos 2\alpha \Big|_{2\alpha=0}^{2\alpha=4\pi} = 2\pi \cos \Delta \alpha. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we arrive at

$$\Delta TDOA_{ij}^2 = \frac{3}{4\pi\Delta x^3 c^2} \Delta x^5 / 5 \cdot I_1(I_2 + I_3 - I_4) = \frac{3}{4\pi\Delta x^3 c^2} \Delta x^5 / 5 \cdot 2(\pi + \pi - 2\pi \cos \Delta\alpha) = 3\Delta x^2 / 5 \cdot (1 - \cos \Delta\alpha) / c^2.$$

Having N microphones configuration (coordinate vectors $\overrightarrow{mic}_i, 1 \leq i \leq N$), the mean squared error of calculation of TDOA becomes:

$$\Delta TDOA(\vec{x}) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{5} \frac{|\Delta x|}{c}} \sqrt{\sum_{i < j}^N (1 - \cos \Delta_{ij}(\vec{x}))} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{20} \frac{|\Delta x|}{c}} \sqrt{N! / (N - 2)! - 2 \sum_{i < j}^N \cos \Delta_{ij}(\vec{x})}$$

Or, in other words, the configuration quality is $\frac{\Delta TDOA(\vec{x})}{\Delta x} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{5}} \sqrt{\sum_{i < j}^N (1 - \cos \Delta_{ij}(\vec{x}))} / c$

Note. This formula describes the TDOA error for sound source in position \vec{x} in terms of the angles Δ_{ij} at which segments $|\overrightarrow{mic}_j - \overrightarrow{mic}_i|$ are viewed from this position \vec{x} .

The theorem is proved.